

USING THE CELLO IN MODERN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the practical and theoretical features of modern cello performance.

Key words: music culture, instrument performance, art, Cello, music history.

The cello is a stringed bowed instrument of the bass and tenor register, known from the first half of the 16th century, of the same structure as the violin or viola, but much larger. The cello has wide expressive possibilities and carefully developed performance technique, it is used as a solo, ensemble and orchestral instrument.

The appearance of the cello dates back to the beginning of the 16th century. Initially, it was used as a bass instrument to accompany singing or playing an instrument of a higher register. There were numerous varieties of the cello, differing from each other in size, number of strings, tuning, most often tuning was lower than the modern one.

In the 17th-18th centuries, the efforts of the outstanding musical masters of the Italian schools (Nicolo Amati, Giuseppe Guarneri, Antonio Stradivari, Carlo Bergonzi, Domenico Montagnana) created a classical cello model with a firmly established body size.

At the end of the 17th century, the first solo works for cello appeared - sonatas and ricercars by Domenico Gabrieli. By the middle of the 18th century, the cello began to be used as a concert instrument, owing to its brighter, fuller sound and improving performance technique, finally displacing the viola da gamba from musical practice. The cello is also part of the symphony orchestra and chamber ensembles. The final assertion of the cello as one of the leading instruments in music occurred in the 20th century through the efforts of the outstanding musician Pau Casals.

In the 21st century, one of the most popular musical trends - symphonic rock - combines elements of progressive rock and classical traditions. This can be either world classics (from simple quoting of some episodes to interpretation of entire works), or in the use of the traditions of classical symphonic music in composition and arrangement of original compositions.

Also in this direction, academic compositions are used (from small ensembles to symphony orchestras), the composition of instruments is strings, woodwinds, percussion, xylophone, and keyboards.

Characteristic features of this genre: Structurally complex compositions, frequent rhythm changes, epic, dense sound, a secondary role of vocals, more often only instrumental music, emotionality.

The origins of this direction are 1964–1967. The first attempts to combine classical music and rock were in the mid-1960s, under the name of baroque rock. At that time they

were prominent representatives of The Beatles, The Rolling Stones. 1968 British band Deep Purple recorded one of the first rock concerts featuring a symphony orchestra.

The heyday of symphonic rock is attributed to the first half of the 1970s - it was the most popular genre. Outstanding representatives of this genre:

Apocalyptica - Early career 1993 Finnish symphonic-rock cello band. The group consists of 4 cellists. Initially famous for instrumental cover versions of compositions by famous thrash metal bands such as Metallica, Kiss, Slipknot, Apocalyptica later began releasing material of its own composition.

2cellos is a Croatian duo of cellists Luka Šulić and Stjepan Hauser.

The group became famous thanks to the video posted on YouTube of a cover version of Michael Jackson's "Smooth Criminal", which gained more than 3 million views in the first 2 weeks, and in general - more than 253 million views (as of 01/17/2016).

On April 12, 2011, the duo signed a contract with Sony Masterworks and an invitation to join Elton John on his world tour.

The German Cello Orchestra "120 Cello" consists of more than 120 musicians. The orchestra's repertoire includes compositions by such groups as Apocalyptica, The Rasmus, HIM, Hoobastank, Nina Hagen.

Rasputina is a musical rock band composed mainly of cellists. The band formed in Brooklyn, New York in 1992 when Melora Krieger advertised for a cello-only band. Cellist Julia Kent responded and the two formed the Traveling Ladies' Cello Society. In 1994, the band toured with Nirvana, and in 1996, under the new name Rasputina, they recorded their first album using only two cellos and a drum kit.

Coppelius playing symphonic rock with drums, double bass, cello and clarinet. Fame came to them on September 28, 2002, at the farewell concert of The Inchtabokatables, where Coppelius played as the opening act. But, according to the musicians, they all come from the 18th century, at the same time the group was founded.

This legend is supported both in interviews and on the website, where there is almost no reliable information about the group. For example, on the official website you can find the "Schedule of concerts in extracts for 1803-1954". During concerts, Coppelius remain true to their style of dress (frock coats, stand-up collars, tailcoats and top hats) and perform with a footman and absinthe. Atmospheric performances are a trademark and one of the reasons for the popularity of the group.

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